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MORE ABOUT $\pi\eta$ -CLOSED SETS

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Abstract: In this paper, we study $\pi\eta$ -closed sets in topological spaces and investigate the relationship with other existing generalized closed sets. Moreover, we also study the concepts of $\pi\eta$ -continuous and almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous functions in topological spaces. We obtain some properties of $\pi\eta$ -closed sets and almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous functions. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be $\pi\eta$ -closed if $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called $\pi\eta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in X for every closed set F of Y . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\eta$ -closed in X for every regular closed set F of Y .

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1. Introduction

In 1937, Stone [15] introduced the notion of regular open sets. In 1963, Levine [8] introduced the concept of semi-open sets. In 1965, Njastad [13] introduced the concept of α -open sets. In 1968, the notion of π -open sets were introduced by Zaitsev [18] which are weak form of regular open sets and Singal and Singal [14] introduced the concept of almost continuous mappings. In 1970, Levine [9] initiated the study of generalized closed (briefly g -closed) sets. In 1973, Carnahan [5] introduced the concept of R -map. In 1974, Arya and Gupta [2] introduced the notion of completely continuity. In 1980, Noiri [12] introduced the concept of δ -continuity. In 1990, Munshi [11] introduced the concept of super continuity. Arya and Nour [3] introduced the notion of g -closed sets. In 1994, Maki et al. [10] introduced the notion of αg -closed sets. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [6] introduced the notion of πg -closed sets, π -continuous and almost π -continuous functions. In 2006, Aslim and Noiri [4] introduced πg -closed sets in topological spaces, In 2007, Arockiarani and Janaki [1] introduced the notion of $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2019, Subbulakshmi, Sumathi, Indirani [16, 17] introduced and investigated the notion of η -open and $g\eta$ -closed sets. In 2021, Kumar [7] introduced the concepts of $\pi\eta$ -closed sets and some related topics as $\pi\eta$ -continuous and almost $\pi\eta$ -continuous and obtained some properties of $\pi\eta$ -closed sets.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** [15] (resp. **regular closed** [15]) if $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [18]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**.

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (i) **semi-open** (briefly **s-open**) [8] if $A \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$.
- (ii) **α -open** [13] if $A \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(A)))$.
- (ii) **η -open** [16] if $A \subset \text{in}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(A))) \cup \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$.
- (iii) **η -closed** [16] if $A \supset \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(A))) \cup \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$.

The complement of a **s-open** (resp. **α -open**) set is called **s-closed** (resp. **α -closed**). The intersection of all s-closed (resp. α -closed, η -closed) sets containing A , is called s-closure (resp. **α -closure**, **η -closure**) of A , and is denoted by **s-cl(A)** (resp. **α -cl(A)**, **η -cl(A)**). The **η -interior** of A , denoted by **η -int(A)** is defined as union of all η -open sets contained in A . We denote the family of all η -open (resp. η -closed) sets of a topological space by **η -O(X)** (resp. **η -C(X)**).

Definition 2.2. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [9] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (2) **πg -closed** [6] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (3) **generalized s-closed** (briefly **gs-closed**) [3] if $\text{s-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.

- (4) **π gs-closed** [4] if $s\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
 (5) **α -generalized closed** (briefly **α g-closed**) [10] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{S}$.
 (6) **π g α -closed** [1] if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
 (7) **generalized η -closed** (briefly **g η -closed**) [17] if $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{S}$.
 (8) **π g η -closed** [7] if $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
 (9) **g-open** (resp. **π g-open**, **gs-open**, **π gs-open**, **α g-open**, **π g α -open**, **g η -open**, **π g η -open**) set if the complement of A is g-closed (resp. π g-closed, gs-closed, π gs-closed, α g-closed, π g α -closed, g η -closed, π g η -closed).

Remark 2.3. From the above definitions and known results the relationship between π g η -closed sets and some other existing generalized closed sets are implemented in the following Figure:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is π gs-closed as well as π g η -closed. But it is neither gs-closed nor π g-closed.

Example 2.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{b\}$ are π gs-closed as well as π g η -closed but not closed.

Example 2.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, c, d\}$ and $B = \{b, c, d\}$ are π gs-closed as well as π g η -closed but not closed.

Example 2.7. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is π g α -closed, π gs-closed as well as π g η -closed. But it is neither closed nor α g-closed.

Example 2.8. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b, c\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are π g-closed, π g α -closed, π gs-closed as well as π g η -closed but not closed.

Example 2.9. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is π g α -closed as well as π g η -closed. But it is neither closed nor g-closed.

Example 2.10. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g-closed, α g-closed, g η -closed, π g α -closed, π gs-closed, π g η -closed. But it is closed.

Example 2.11. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is η -closed as well as π g η -closed but not α -closed.

Example 2.12. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is g η -closed as well as π g η -closed but not closed.

3. π g η -closure and π g η -interior

Definition 3.1. For any set $A \subset X$, the **π g η -closure** of A is defined as the intersection of all π g η -closed sets containing A . We write

$$\pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A) = \{F : A \subset F \text{ and } F \text{ is } \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-closed set in } X\}$$

Definition 3.2. The **π g η -interior** of A , denoted by **π g η -int(A)** is defined as union of all π g η -open sets contained in A . We write

$$\pi\text{g}\eta\text{-int}(A) = \{G : A \supset G \text{ and } G \text{ is } \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-open set in } X\}$$

Lemma:3.3. For an $x \in X$, $x \in \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A)$ if and only if $V \cap A \neq \phi$ for every π g η -open set V containing x .

Proof. First, let us suppose that there exists a π g η -open set V containing x such that $V \cap A = \phi$. Since $A \subset X - V$, $\pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset X - V \Rightarrow x \notin \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A)$, which is a contradiction to the fact that $x \in \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A)$. Hence $V \cap A \neq \phi$ for every π g η -open set V containing x .

On the other hand, let $x \notin \pi\text{g}\eta\text{-cl}(A)$. Then there exists a π g η -closed subset F containing A such that $x \notin F$. Then $x \in X - F$

and $X - F$ is $\pi g\eta$ -open. Also, $(X - F) \cap A \neq \emptyset$, a contradiction. Hence the lemma.

Lemma 3.4. Let A and B be subsets of (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then

- (i) $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$ and $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X) = X$.
- (ii) If $A \subset B$, then $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B)$.
- (iii) $A \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A)$.
- (iv) $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) = \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A))$.
- (v) $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cup B) = \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \cup \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B)$.

Proof. Obvious.

Remark 3.5. If $A \subset X$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed, then $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) = A$. But the converse is need not be true as seen in following example.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{a\}$, $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) = \{a\} = A$, but $A = \{a\}$ is not $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X .

Lemma 3.7. Let A and B be subsets of X . Then $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B)$.

Proof. Since $A \cap B \subset A, B$.

$$\Rightarrow \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A), \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B)$$

$$\Rightarrow \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B).$$

Remark 3.8. The converse of the above need not be true as seen in following example.

Example 3.9. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{e\}, \{a, e\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{c, d, e\}\}$. Let $A = \{a, c, e\} \subset X, B = \{d\} \subset X$. Then $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) = \{a, b, c, e\}$, $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B) = \{b, d\}$. But $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B) = \{b\} \not\subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B)$.

Remark 3.10. We denote $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets in topological space by $\pi g\eta\text{-C}(X)$ and $\pi g\eta$ -open sets by $\pi g\eta\text{-O}(X)$.

Definition 3.11. $\mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta} = \{V \subset X : \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - V) = X - V\}$

Theorem: 3.12. If $\pi g\eta\text{-O}(X)$ is topology, then $\mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}$ is a topology.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Clearly, } \emptyset, X &\in \mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}. \text{ Let } \{A_i : i \in A\} \in \mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}. \\ \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - (\cup A_i)) &= \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(\cap (X - A_i)) \\ &\subset \cap \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - A_i) \\ &= \cap (X - A_i) \\ &= X - \cup A_i \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\cup A_i \in \mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}$.

Let $A, B \in \mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - (A \cap B)) &= \pi g\eta\text{-cl}((X - A) \cup (X - B)) \\ &= \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - A) \cup \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - B) \\ &= (X - A) \cup (X - B) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $A \cap B \in \mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}$ and hence $\mathfrak{T}^*_{\pi g\eta}$ is a topology.

Definition 3.13. Let X be a topological space and let $x \in X$. A subset N of X is said to be **$\pi g\eta$ -neighbourhood** of x if there exists a $\pi g\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

Definition. 3.14. Let A be a subset of X . A point $x \in A$ is said to be **$\pi g\eta$ -interior** point of A if A is a $\pi g\eta$ -nbhd of x . The set of all $\pi g\eta$ -interior of A and is denoted by $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$.

Theorem: 3.15. If A be a subset of X . Then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is } \pi g\eta\text{-open, } G \subset A\}$

Proof. Straight forward.

Theorem 3.16. Let A and B be subsets of X . Then

- (i) $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(X) = X$ and $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.
- (ii) $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \subset A$.
- (iii) If B is any $\pi g\eta$ -open set contained in A , then $B \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$.
- (iv) If $A \subset B$, then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$.
- (v) $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)) = \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$.

Proof. Straight forward.

Theorem 3.17. If a subset A of a space X is $\pi g\eta$ -open, then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) = A$.

Proof. Obvious.

Remark 3.18. The converse of the above need not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 3.19. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Let $A = \{c, d\}$. Then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) = \{c, d\} = A$. But $A = \{c, d\}$ is not $\pi g\eta\text{-open}$.

Theorem 3.20. If A and B are subsets of X , then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cup \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cup B)$.

Proof. We know that $A \subset A \cup B$ and $B \subset A \cup B$. Then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cup B)$, $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cup B)$. Hence $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cup \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cup B)$.

Theorem 3.21. If A and B are subsets of a space X , then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B) = \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$

Proof. We know that $A \cap B \subset A$, $A \cap B \subset B$. Then $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$ and $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$.

$\Rightarrow \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B) = \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$(1)

Again, let $x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$. Then $x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$ and $x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$. Hence x is a $\pi g\eta\text{-interior}$ point of each of sets A and B . It follows that A and B are $\pi g\eta\text{-nbhds}$ of x , so that their intersection $A \cap B$ is also a $\pi g\eta\text{-nbhd}$ of x . Hence $x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B)$.

Thus, $x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B) \Rightarrow x \in \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B)$.

Therefore, $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B)$(2)

From (1) and (2), $\pi g\eta\text{-int}(A \cap B) = \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A) \cap \pi g\eta\text{-int}(B)$.

Theorem 3.22. If A is subset of X , then

- (i) $\eta\text{-int}(A) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)$ and
- (ii) $(X - \pi g\eta\text{-int}(A)) = \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(X - A)$ and $(X - \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A)) = \pi g\eta\text{-int}(X - A)$.

Proof. Straight forward.

4. $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ and almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ functions

Definition 4.1. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called:

- (a) **R-map** [5] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed in X for every regular closed set F of Y .
- (b) **completely continuous** [2] (resp. **super continuous** [11]) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed (resp. $\delta\text{-closed}$) in X for every closed set F of Y .
- (c) **$\pi\text{-continuous}$** [6] (resp. **$\eta\text{-continuous}$** [17], **$g\eta\text{-continuous}$** [17], **$\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$** [7]) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\text{-closed}$ (resp. $\eta\text{-closed}$, $g\eta\text{-closed}$, $\pi g\eta\text{-closed}$) in X for every closed set F of Y .
- (d) **almost $\pi\text{-continuous}$** [6] (resp. **$\delta\text{-continuous}$** [12], **almost continuous** [14], **almost $\eta\text{-continuous}$** , **almost $g\eta\text{-continuous}$** , **almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$** [7]) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\text{-closed}$ (resp. $\delta\text{-closed}$, closed, $\eta\text{-closed}$, $g\eta\text{-closed}$, $\pi g\eta\text{-closed}$) in X for every regular closed set F of Y .
- (e) **$\pi g\eta\text{-irresolute}$** [7] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\eta\text{-closed}$ in X for every $\pi g\eta\text{-closed}$ set F of Y .

Example 4.2. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{x, y\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{x\}, \{x, z\}\}$. The identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ is an R-map as well as almost $\pi\text{-continuous}$. It is also $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ and almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ but not continuous.

Example 4.3. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$. The identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ is continuous as well as $\eta\text{-continuous}$ but not $\delta\text{-continuous}$.

Example 4.4. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$ and define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ as follows: $f(x) = f(y) = x$ and $f(z) = z$. Then f is $\pi\text{-continuous}$, $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ and almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ but not R-map.

Example 4.5. Let $X = \{x, y, z, w\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}, \{x, y, z\}, \{x, y, w\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ as follows: $f(x) = z$, $f(y) = x$, $f(z) = y$ and $f(w) = z$. Then f is almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$.

Example 4.6. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}\}$, $Y = \{a, b\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{a\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = f(z) = b$ and $f(y) = a$. Then f is $g\eta\text{-continuous}$ as well as $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$. It is almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$ but not continuous.

Example 4.7. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then $f^{-1}(\{z\}) = \{y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{x, z\}) = \{x, y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y, z\}) = \{y, z\}$. Therefore, f is $g\eta\text{-continuous}$ as well as $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$. It is almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$.

Example 4.8. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{y, z\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then f is $g\eta\text{-continuous}$ as well as $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$. It is almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$.

Example 4.9. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{y, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\emptyset, Y, \{x\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = y$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = x$. Then f is $g\eta\text{-continuous}$ as well as $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$. It is almost $\pi g\eta\text{-continuous}$.

Example 4.10. Let $X = Y = \{x, y, z\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{x\}, \{z\}, \{x, z\}\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, Y, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{x, y\}\}$. Define $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \rho)$ as follows: $f(x) = x$, $f(y) = z$ and $f(z) = y$. Then $f^{-1}(\{x\}) = \{x\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y\}) = \{z\}$, $f^{-1}(\{z\}) = \{y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{x, z\}) = \{x, y\}$, $f^{-1}(\{y, z\}) = \{y, z\}$. Since inverse image of every $g\eta$ -open set in Y is $g\eta$ -open in X . Therefore, f is $g\eta$ -continuous as well as $\pi g\eta$ -continuous. It is almost $\pi g\eta$ -continuous

Remark 4.2. From the above definitions, proposition and known results, we have following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the above examples:

5. Properties of $\pi g\eta$ -continuous functions

Definition 5.1. A topological space X is called a **$\pi g\eta$ - $T_{1/2}$ space** [7] if every $\pi g\eta$ -closed set is η -closed.

Theorem 5.2. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a function, then the following are equivalent:

- (a) f is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.
 (b) The inverse image of every open set in Y is $\pi g\eta$ -open in X .

Proof. Follows from the definitions.

Theorem 5.3. If $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous, then $f(\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(A))$ for every subset A of X .

Proof. Let $A \subset X$. Since f is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous and $A \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}(f(A)))$, we obtain $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}(f(A)))$ and then $f(\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(A))$.

Remark 5.4. The converse of the above need not be true as seen in following example.

Example 5.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $\sigma = \{\phi, X, \{c, d\}\}$. Let $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \sigma)$ be an identity map. Let $A = \{a, b\}$. Then $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(\{a, b\}) = \{a, b\} \subset f^{-1}(\text{cl}(f(\{a, b\}))) = X$. But $f^{-1}(\{a, b\}) = \{a, b\}$ is not $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . Hence f is not $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Proposition 5.6. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a $\pi g\eta$ -continuous function and H be π -open, $\pi g\eta$ -closed subset of X . Assume that $\pi g\eta\text{-C}(X, \tau)$ closed under finite intersections. Then the restriction be $f/H : (H, \tau/H) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Proof. Let F be any η -closed subset in Y . By hypothesis and our assumption $f^{-1}(F) \cap H_1$, it is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . Since $(f/H)^{-1}(F) = H_1$, it is sufficient to show that H_1 is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in H . Let $H_1 \subset G_1$ is any π -open set in H . We know that a subset A of X is open, then $\pi\text{-O}(A, \tau/A) = \{V \cap A : V \in \pi\text{O}(X, \tau)\} \dots \dots \dots (1)$. By (1), $G_1 = G \cap H$ for some π -open set G in X .

Then $H_1 \subset G_1 \subset G$ and H_1 is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X implies $\eta\text{-cl}_X(H_1) = \eta\text{-cl}_X(H_1) \cap H \subset G \cap H = G_1$ and so H_1 is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in H . Therefore, f/H is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Generalization of Pasting Lemma for $\pi g\eta$ -continuous functions.

Theorem 5.7. Let $X = G \cup H$ be a topological space with topology τ and Y be a topological space with topology σ . Let $f : (G, \tau/G) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and $g : (H, \tau/H) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be $\pi g\eta$ -continuous functions such $f(x) = g(x)$ for every $x \in G \cap H$. Suppose that both G and H are π -open and $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . Then their combination $(f \vee g) : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ defined by $(f \vee g)(x) = f(x)$ if $x \in G$ and $(f \vee g)(x) = g(x)$ if $x \in H$ is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Proof. Let F be any closed set in Y . Clearly $(f \vee g)^{-1}(F) = f^{-1}(F) \cup g^{-1}(F)$. Since $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in G and G is π -open in X and $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X , $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -closed in X . Similarly, $g^{-1}(F)$ is π -open in X . Therefore, $(f \vee g)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -continuous.

Proposition 5.8. If a function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is $\pi g\eta$ -irresolute, then

- (i) $f(\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \pi g\eta\text{-cl}(f(A))$ for every subset A of X .
 (ii) $\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subset f^{-1}(\pi g\eta\text{-cl}(B))$ for every subset B of Y .

Proof.

(i) For every $A \subset X$, $\pi\eta\text{-cl}(f(A))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in Y . By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(A))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X . Also, $A \subset f^{-1}(f(A)) \subset f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(A))$. By the definition of $\pi\eta\text{-closure}$, we have $\pi\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(A))$. Hence, we get $f(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \pi\eta\text{-cl}(f(A))$.

(ii) $\pi\eta\text{-cl}(B)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in Y and so by hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(B))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X . Since $f^{-1}(B) \subset f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(B))$, it follows that $\pi\eta\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subset f^{-1}(\pi\eta\text{-cl}(B))$.

Theorem 5.9. For a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent to one another:

- (i) f is almost $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$.
- (ii) $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X for every regular open set V of Y .
- (iii) $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X for every open set V of Y .
- (iv) $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X for every closed set V of Y .

Proof.

(i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let V be a regular open subset of Y . Since $Y - V$ is regular closed and f is almost $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$, then $f^{-1}(Y - V) = X - f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X . Thus $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ on X .

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Let V be a regular closed subset of Y . Then $Y - V$ is regular open. By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(Y - V) = X - f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X . Then $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ and hence f is almost $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let V be an open subset of Y . Then $\text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ is regular open. By hypothesis $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X .

(iii) \Rightarrow (ii). Let V be a regular open subset of Y . Since $Y - \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$ and every regular open set is open, then $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X .

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Let V be a closed subset of Y . Then $Y - V$ is open. By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(Y - V))) = f^{-1}(Y - \text{cl}(\text{int}(V))) = X - f^{-1}(Y - \text{cl}(\text{int}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X . Hence $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X .

(iv) \Rightarrow (iii). Let V be an open subset of Y . Then $Y - V$ is closed. By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(Y - V))) = f^{-1}(Y - \text{cl}(\text{int}(V))) = X - f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X . Hence $f^{-1}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(V)))$ is $\pi\eta\text{-open}$ in X .

Proposition 5.10. If f is $\pi\eta\text{-irresolute}$, then it is almost- $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$.

Proof. Straight forward.

Definition 5.11. A function $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is called a **$\pi\text{-open map}$** [6] if $f(U)$ is $\pi\text{-open}$ in (Y, σ) for every $\pi\text{-open}$ set U in (X, τ) .

Proposition 5.12. If f is bijective, $\pi\text{-open}$, almost- $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$, then f is $\pi\eta\text{-irresolute}$.

Proof. Let F be a $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ set of Y . Let $f^{-1}(F) \subset U$, where U is $\pi\text{-open}$ in X . Then $F \subset f(U)$. Since f is $\pi\text{-open}$, $f(U)$ is $\pi\text{-open}$ in Y , F is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ set in Y and $F \subset f(U) \Rightarrow \eta\text{-cl}(F) \subset f(U)$. (i. e) $f^{-1}(\eta\text{-cl}(F)) \subset U$. Since f is almost- $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$, $\eta\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(\eta\text{-cl}(F))) \subset U$.

So, $\eta\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(F)) \subset \eta\text{-cl}(f^{-1}(\eta\text{-cl}(F))) \subset U$.

$\Rightarrow f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi\eta\text{-closed}$ in X . Hence f is $\pi\eta\text{-irresolute}$.

Proposition 5.13. If f is bijective, $\pi\text{-open}$, $R\text{-map}$, then f is $\pi\eta\text{-irresolute}$.

Proof. Since f is an $R\text{-map}$, it is almost $\pi\eta\text{-continuous}$. By **Proposition 5.13**, f is $\pi\eta\text{-irresolute}$.

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